

IMPROVEMENT OF THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING PEN DRAWING IN THE SYSTEM OF HIGHER PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION ON THE BASIS OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *In this article, based on today's demand, a person with open eyes will definitely see the changes in education. The science of visual arts is considered the oldest among types of art. Humanity appeared to paint. Through images, they express their dreams and thoughts. A clear example of this is the masterpieces of art found in Sarmishsay rock and other places.*

Keywords: *modern education, innovative technologies, creative thinking, creative ability, modern program, online platform, interactive material, multimedia tools, innovative approach, aesthetic thinking, practical skills, increasing motivation, raising the methodological level of teachers.*

1. Relevance of the topic:

Art education occupies an important place in the modern education system. The pencil is important in the use of innovative technologies in teaching visual arts, in the development of students' creative thinking, and in increasing their interest in visual arts.

2. Purpose of the topic:

The main purpose of this research is to study and suggest how to effectively use modern technologies in teaching pencil drawing.

3. The importance of modern technologies in the educational process

Modern technologies, including multimedia tools, interactive programs and online platforms make the educational process interactive and interesting. This increases the effectiveness of the educational process.

4. Research methods:

- Theoretical research: study of teaching methods and modern technologies.
- Practical research: experience of using modern technologies in the educational process.

Through this foundation, it is aimed to reveal the possibilities of using modern technologies in the process of teaching the science of pencil drawing.

The aim is to improve the method of teaching pencil drawing based on modern technologies. It aims to use innovative tools in the teaching process, develop students' creative abilities, and more effectively acquire knowledge in science. modern programs, online platforms and interactive materials will be developed within the scope of the goal. Based on the results of the research, recommendations are made for improving teaching methods.

This study examines the role of multimedia tools, interactive programs and online platforms in the educational process. It is important to develop students' creative thinking skills, improve their aesthetic thinking and strengthen their practical skills with the help of innovative approaches in the educational process. Existing problems, including increasing the motivation of students and raising the methodological level of teachers, ensure the relevance of this goal. The

results of the research will help to introduce innovations in the educational system and increase interest in pencil art.

The expected results show the effectiveness of using modern technologies in the process of teaching pencil drawing. These results serve to scientifically develop the educational methodology, increase creative abilities and motivation of students. Their social importance is aimed at increasing the interest in art among students, as well as improving the quality of education through innovative approaches. The planned results are consistent with world-class research, which can lead to changes in global education systems. In the economic and social spheres, these results provide opportunities for implementation, effective use of educational resources, and improvement of the quality of art education.

It should be noted that the use of modern technologies in teaching pencil drawing can radically change the educational process. Innovative methods create an interactive environment for students, develop their creative thinking and increase their interest in visual arts. Multimedia tools and online platforms play a big role in strengthening students' knowledge. Also, this approach helps to update the pedagogical methods of teachers, adapting them to modern requirements. As a result, the educational process becomes more effective and interesting, and serves to reveal the creative potential of students. This, in turn, has a positive effect on improving the quality of art education and the global development of the education system.

Technologically, the use of modern tools in teaching the science of pencil drawing makes the educational process interactive and effective. Multimedia programs, virtual reality and interactive applications create new opportunities for students, involve them in the creative process. For example, with the help of graphic design programs, students learn to express their ideas visually. Also, online platforms will expand teaching methods and distance learning opportunities. With the help of such technologies, students will have the opportunity to join the global art community, share their work and learn on a global scale. As a result, teaching pencil drawing meets modern requirements and increases the quality of the educational process. These technological innovations are taking the future of art education to new heights.

From a socio-economic point of view, the pencil drawing is important in teaching the science of image with the help of modern technologies, in the development of the educational system and in the improvement of social skills. By developing creative skills, students acquire skills that meet the requirements of the modern labor market. This increases their employment and contributes to economic stability. In turn, the need for specialists in the field of art and design has a positive effect on social development. Also, access to art education will be expanded through modern technologies, which will create equal educational conditions for all social strata. As a result, the development of art and culture also serves to increase aesthetic values in society, which further enriches the social environment.

It became the basis for the introduction of innovative methods in teaching art in the modern education system. The innovative aspects of the project are that new educational programs were developed based on the experiences gained and the teaching methodology was updated with the help of modern technologies. This process created an interesting and interactive learning environment for students.

It is planned to carry out new research aimed at improving the methodology of teaching the science of pencil drawing in the future. In turn, these studies, based on the results of previous projects, are aimed at expanding innovative technologies and methods. In this, it is envisaged to

use interactive platforms, video lessons and virtual reality technologies so that students can do their creative work more effectively.

These new studies, based on previous findings, will further strengthen the role of pencil art in the educational process and serve to increase interest in art. As a result, the project combines scientific principles, practical approaches and innovative methods to increase the effectiveness of the educational process. This creates an opportunity to make changes in the education system in the future and serves to develop creative abilities.

Summary:

Modern technologies play an important role in improving the teaching methodology of pencil drawing. By making the educational process interactive and interesting, opportunities to develop students' creative abilities are created.

Recommendations:

1. To train teachers on modern technologies.
2. To update educational programs and enrich with modern tools.
3. To create online platforms for showing students' creative works.

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